

“Be like others”: On what search engines tell us about our nations

Vihang Jumle^a, Mykola Makhortykh^a and Maryna Sydorova^a

^a *Institute of Communication and Media Studies, University of Bern, Switzerland*

1. Introduction

Scholars have increasingly grown sceptical of how internet platforms have become indispensable intermediaries in people’s lives in enabling their access to information (Gillespie, 2010, 2014b, 2019; Mihelj, 2023). While the “curatorial logic” of these platforms eases navigating the internet, scholars suggest that, in due process, they inevitably also become channels of interventions for commercial and political actors on national lines (Mihelj, 2023: 13). Apps like Douyin or Baidu are a case in point that are instrumentalised by various state actors to intervene in national ideas and reproduce in their users a specific form of nationality (Chen, Kaye and Zeng, 2021). This nexus, where internet platforms co-opt with commercial and political actors to produce such national interventions (in an increasingly nationalised infrastructure), is termed ‘Platform Nations’ (Mihelj, 2023).

What is less understood within this framework is the role of Western commercial platforms, like Google, which tend to evade such political instrumentalisation, play. The extant literature documents that such platforms, as a function of only its commercial logic, too can reach the same ends in producing and reinforcing socio-cultural biases (on race, political representation, gender, etc.) and, hence, can potentially also produce on national identities and ideas (Kay, Matuszek and Munson, 2015; Rohrbach, Makhortykh and Sydorova, 2024; Urman and Makhortykh, 2023). The nuances of this form of representation are yet to be explored.

To uncover this research end, we query Google Images with 10 different queries (English and Hindi, five each) from three locations (Mumbai, New Delhi and the US) and compare the representation of three constitutive electoral components: political personalities, socio-cultural symbols and citizen groups. Our research question was: What are the differences in the visual representation of the Indian elections in 2024 along the axis of search language and search location?

The intersecting axes of search language and location can broadly come to overlap with various demographic groups. For instance, search combination of English and US can correspond to international users or Indian diaspora in the US. Whereas a search contrast of English versus Hindi can come to overlap with class groups in India, where language tends to be notable segregator. By splitting the visual representation over these axes, we analyse how the same subject – the elections – is mediated for different groups, more so, for the same population resident within the same national boundary. While we expect that there will indeed be difference in representation, we are unaware of what these differences be about. Our findings flesh out these representative differences over the three aforementioned categories.

We discuss three points: first, what are the interpretations and consequences of observing contrasting representations across the semi-localised case (English-India) and fully localised case (Hindi-India)? Second, what are the pathways that can explain these varying representations? If instrumentalised

platforms serve the state apparatus, whom can we induct the commercial platform serve from this case study? Third, in a condition of such localised representation, how can users who rely on search to acquire political information form justified beliefs (Miller and Record, 2013)?

We conclude with some ideas on how search engines architecture could evolve to balance their commercial and social responsibility and with some limitation of our study.

Table 1

List of queries

English	Hindi
Indian elections 2024	भारतीय चुनाव 2024
Parliament india 2024	संसद भारत 2024
national elections india 2024	भारत में राष्ट्रीय चुनाव 2024
lok sabha elections 2024	लोकसभा चुनाव 2024
voting in india 2024	भारत में मतदान 2024

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